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ENTREPRENEURIAL USE OF GAMIFICATION FOR KNOWLEDGE SHARING INSIDE ORGANIZATION; A PUBLIC SERVICE MEDIA FROM MIDDLE EAST

USO EMPRESARIAL DE LA *GAMIFICACIÓN* PARA EL INTERCAMBIO DE CONOCIMIENTO DENTRO DE LA ORGANIZACIÓN: MEDIOS DE COMUNICACIÓN DEL SERVICIO PÚBLICO DE ORIENTE MEDIO

ABSTRACT

Knowledge as an organizational resource in media businesses has become increasingly important in a competitive environment. There is a growing interest in developing new techniques to enhance knowledge sharing between people, that is conducive to media entrepreneurs. One of the main barriers to knowledge sharing in communicating entrepreneurs is the lack of motivation which can be improved by using gamification. The aim of this research is to achieve a better understanding of the gamified knowledge sharing process to improve organizational entrepreneurship among TV employees. We conducted semi-structured interviews with 15 employees and managers of the IRIB organization. Qualitative analysis of the research data was conducted in three steps: transcribing data, coding and organizing categories. Most of IRIB's employees inspired by intrinsic motivations include status, power, learning, autonomy, and community. Security is the only and most critical extrinsic motivation in IRIB organization. Moreover, we have found four categories of user types, namely achiever, socializer, discoverer, and survivor. Our study identified the main motivators of media staff that create a sense of happiness and motivation to participate in organizational entrepreneurship via knowledge sharing. Finally, we offer new insights about the media employees' user types in the gamified knowledge sharing system.

KEYWORDS

Organizational entrepreneurship, Corporate entrepreneurship, Media entrepreneurship, Gamification, Knowledge sharing.

RESUMEN

El conocimiento como recurso organizacional en las empresas de medios de comunicación se ha vuelto cada vez más importante en los entornos competitivos. Existe un interés creciente en el desarrollo de nuevas técnicas para mejorar el intercambio de conocimientos entre las personas, lo que favorece a los emprendedores de los medios de comunicación. Una de las principales barreras para el intercambio de conocimientos en la comunicación de los emprendedores es la falta de motivación, que puede mejorarse mediante la *gamificación*. El objetivo de esta investigación es lograr una mejor comprensión del proceso de intercambio de conocimientos de *gamificación* para mejorar el emprendimiento organizacional entre los empleados de la televisión. Realizamos entrevistas semiestructuradas con 15 empleados y

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gerentes de la organización IRIB. El análisis cualitativo de los datos de la investigación se realizó en tres pasos: transcripción de datos, codificación y organización de categorías. La mayoría de los empleados de IRIB se inspiran por motivaciones intrínsecas que incluyen estatus, poder, aprendizaje, autonomía y comunidad. La seguridad es la única y más crítica motivación extrínseca en la organización IRIB. Además, hemos encontrado cuatro categorías de tipos de usuarios, a saber: triunfador, socializador, descubridor y sobreviviente. Nuestro estudio identificó las principales motivaciones que crean un sentido de felicidad y motivación en el personal de los medios de comunicación para participar en el emprendimiento organizacional a través del intercambio de conocimientos. Por último, ofrecemos nuevos conocimientos sobre los tipos de usuarios de los empleados de medios de comunicación en el sistema de intercambio de conocimientos de *gamificación*.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Emprendimiento Organizacional, Emprendimiento Corporativo, Emprendimiento de Medios, Gamificación, Intercambio de Conocimiento.

INTRODUCTION

In a competitive and unpredictable environment, media companies have to employ organizational sources, such as knowledge, in order to adapt to changes (Roshandel Arbatani et al., 2018; Costello & Oliver, 2018a; Eisape, 2020; Labafi et al., 2017; Murschetz et al., 2020; Nel, et al., 2020; Powers & Zhao, 2019; Roblek et al., 2014; Salamzadeh et al., 2019) and to create organizational value by extracting opportunities (Bali & Zarea, 2018; Khajeheian, 2018; Labafi, 2017; Sharifi et al., 2019; Omar Bali et al., 2020) .

Knowledge is widely spread among media employees, and entrepreneurship depends on the sum of individuals' contributions (Kuratko, Ireland and Hornsby, 2001). A Media organization needs an appropriate motivational system, because employees at state-owned media agencies or public-funded agencies may differ in their motivations to share knowledge (Costello & Oliver, 2018b; Tajeddin et al., 2018). Motivation is considered as one of the important factors of communication between people in entrepreneurial teams, and the diversity of people's incentives should be addressed by good motivational system (Mládková et al., 2015) . According to Dale (2014) "what motivates one person may have the opposite effect on someone else. To this end, it is important to recognize the different motivational triggers" and user type. All people in firms are not sociable or altruistic in knowledge sharing (Andriessen, 2006; Dale, 2014) while, their motives are not limited to monetary incentives (Hendriks, 1999). A good employee engagement program in the organization allows employees to unlock their potentials, increase commitment and enhance their sense of well-being that is conducive to innovative products (Costello & Oliver, 2018b; Rožman et al., 2017).

There is a growing interest in developing new techniques to enhance knowledge sharing between people, that is conducive to creating innovative products (Mládková et al., 2015). In recent years, gamification gained a lot of interest in business fields (Swacha, 2015). Gamified programs addressed the challenges by adding enjoyment, funny layer and game mechanics that provide reciprocal benefits and motivational drivers to beneficiaries (Silic & Back, 2017) and also by attracting employees for engaging in the entrepreneurial process (Emami et al., 2020).

As a media organisation, the Islamic Republic of Iran Broadcasting (IRIB), as a media organization, operates in a highly competitive environment and needs to be innovative in processes and products (Karimi & Salavatian, 2018; Sharifi et al., 2019; Salavatian et al., 2020). The question raised here is how a TV network can collect employees' creativity at the corporate entrepreneurship level by motivating them to participate in the gamified knowledge sharing process. In the entrepreneurial approach, knowledge sharing and its elements, such as motivation, in public service broadcasting are important in responding to environmental changes (Labafi et al., 2017). Thus, in this paper, we studied the gamified knowledge sharing system as a possible and efficient solution to address the current problems of entrepreneurship in the IRIB organization. Research questions are as follows:

RQ1: What are the main motivational needs of TV employees of IRIB to engage in the knowledge sharing process as collective entrepreneurship?

RQ2: What are the User-Types of TV employees of IRIB in the knowledge sharing process as collective entrepreneurship?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowledge sharing

Foss et al. (2010), defined knowledge sharing as a "provision and reception of know-what and know-how performing tasks among organizational members". Van Den Hooff & Ridder (2004), define knowledge sharing as "a process that consists of both pieces of knowledge bringing (donating) and getting (collecting). Knowledge donating, communicating to others what one's intellectual capital is; and knowledge collecting, consulting colleagues to get them to share their intellectual capital." In Hendriks (1999) knowledge sharing definition, "knowledge sharing presumes a relation between at least two parties, one that possesses the knowledge and the other that acquires knowledge. The first party should communicate its knowledge, consciously and willingly or not, in some forms or others (either by acts, by speech, or in writing, etc.), The other party should be able to perceive these expressions of knowledge and make sense of them. In this definition, reconstruction of knowledge is needed to learn by the receiver.

Drucker's prediction about the new economy in the media management literature is critical, which points to the knowledge of employee and the ability to apply this resource in the creative process (Artero & Manfredi, 2015); it came true with the emergence of concepts and approaches such as knowledge-based resources and intellectual capital that provide new business areas for media firms. Unlike property-based resources, knowledge-based resources helped to stable performance in an uncertain and unpredictable environment (Artero & Manfredi, 2015; Labafi, 2017; Miller & Shamsie, 1996; Su & Zarea, 2020), which is relatively unique (Khajeheian, 2016; Oliver, 2016). Knowledge in media firms is considered as a valuable asset to gain competitive advantage (Khajeheian & Ebrahimi, 2020; Misci & Uzunoglu, 2008), respond to the needs of consumers and tackle the problems of industries, so the

development of organizational culture and convincing employees to get more engaged in sharing their knowledge with each other is required (Faustino & Ribeiro, 2015; Roblek et al., 2014).

Limited innovative ideas emerge while many creative people work inside media organization such as television, emphasized the need for the management of media professionals who have distinct capabilities for the success of firms (Artero & Manfredi, 2015; Khajeheian & Friedrichsen, 2017). In other words, media expertise and skills that are stemming from work experience and facing challenges tend to rest on tacit capabilities (Dwyer, 2015; Küng, 2008). An organization cannot be aware of these capabilities unless the individual puts them to use (Misci & Uzunoglu, 2008).

Knowledge sharing as an essential process of generating new ideas and creative media products in media firms (Labafi & Williams, 2018) transforms individual knowledge into organizational knowledge. Participation of employees in this learning process and sharing their knowledge and their ideas, facilitate solving problems and developing new ideas (Harjanti & Noerchoidah, 2017; Hendriks, 1999; Labafi et al., 2017; Lin, 2007). The use of knowledge sharing tools promotes organizational citizenship behavior among the personnel (Emami et al., 2019; Estiri et al., 2018).

Given the issues discussed in this research, the authors chose a definition of knowledge sharing in which knowledge donors and knowledge recipients collaborate to solve problems and create new ideas that led to creating knowledge-based media content. The donation of knowledge is related to the production of media content and communication with colleagues about their intellectual abilities while receiving knowledge is about requesting colleagues to share their intellectual capital.

Motivation

Mierzejewska (2011) argues that the attention of the media management scholars to motivation is negligible. However, in other areas, many studies indicate organisational processes and activities are successful when members of the organization participate in the learning process (Law et al., 2017). The flow of knowledge turns the organization into a creative place (Misci & Uzunoglu, 2008) that leads to finding new, creative and effective ideas. Because Public Broadcast Service organizations compete with private and nonprofit media organizations, the flow of knowledge in these organizations, notably in the IRIB as a traditional media organization, is critical.

Considering the increasing role of audiences in the co-creation of value in public service broadcasts (Khajeheian & Ebrahimi, 2020; Khajeheian & Tadayoni, 2016), and also in sharing information as user-generated content in the areas that previously were exclusively used by public service broadcasts (Kamboj et al., 2018), the necessity of motivating personnel to share their knowledge becomes more important. A critical question from classical to contemporary management theories is “how to motivate

employees to share their knowledge?" To answer this question, there needs to be more focus on motivation theories and practices from Maslow's needs hierarchy to Self-determination theory, and also their impact on people's willingness to share knowledge. Hall (2001) argues that organization motivational strategies should offer different alternatives for those engaged in the knowledge sharing process. An employee can win "hard" reward such as money, salary increase and other services. Alternatively, "soft" reward such as belonging to a community, recognition and personal satisfaction drive employees to share their knowledge.

In the field of management, motivation theories are categorized into Content or Process type. Content-based theories address the internal individual factors; in contrast, process-based theories focus on how individual behaviors have been affected (De Vito et al., 2018). In content theories, the most popular and well-known theory is Maslow's needs hierarchy (Hendriks, 1999). Nowadays, in some cases, Maslow's hierarchy of needs can offer appropriate practices for an organization suffering from employees' lack of motivation, particularly for those who desire tangible rewards such as salary and safety (De Vito et al., 2016).

Based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs, manager, in addition to the basic needs, can respond to the developmental needs of employees throughout their career progressions. So, at the bottom of the hierarchy, there are physiological needs, likes high salaries. In the second tier, the employee wants safety and security in the workplace (Goodarzi et al., 2018). These two tiers are essential in job design. The need to belong to a community that improves efficiency with a supportive and collaborative workplace is in the third tier. In Forth tier, the need for esteem indicates that employee likes to be recognized by co-worker and others for their achievement and hard work. The need for self-actualization is on the top of Maslow's hierarchy (De Vito et al., 2016). Both of Stotn and Walker and Tampoe studies show that motivations for knowledge sharing rather than money or good relationships with co-workers, come from the three highest tiers of hierarchy and are related to self-actualization (Hendriks, 1999).

On the other hand, Hendriks (1999).argues that Maslow's hierarchy of needs has been criticized in some cases; such as the hierarchy of needs doesn't cover how behavior is affected. In spite of criticism to Maslow's theory, the reason why authors choose this theory is to identify motivational needs of the employee. (Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012) argued that a good design process melds creativity and structure to match people's needs with technical feasibility and business realities. Additionally, based on (Dale, 2014) study, identifying personality types and motivational needs are important in the design of the motivational system. Because employees are in different characteristics categories, so any kind of motivation does not have the same effect on different characteristics.

Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan (2012) offer a design framework for developing gamified systems, and within this framework, the players should be identified. It should be noted that not all users are the same, and also, there are World of Warcraft players who do nothing but engage in player-to-player combat and others who spend all of their time exploring the world through solo quests. Similarly, gamified platforms can appeal in different ways to different groups (Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012). To design the gamified knowledge sharing system in this research, a user type model is needed.

Rod King in his Business Model Gamification (King, 2013) catered a useful reference about user-types and categorized his hierarchy based on Maslow's theory in four user-type (see Figure 1). King's model is used in this research because it identified the survivor type of user, which was not mentioned in previous models:

Achiever: achievers love the rush of leveling up or earning a badge (Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012). An achiever in Amy J Kim's work is identified as Express. Self-expression is a popular User-type in gamification and modern social gaming and social media that must be considered by game designer and manager of the organization in motivating people. This type of people enjoys showing who they are by their abilities, and status (Dale, 2014)

Socializer: Socializers want to engage with friends (Salamzadeh et al., 2017; Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012) and be part of an organization as a community that is larger than people. Socializers like to share with others in victories. Collaboration is the main foundation of Q&A systems and social media (Dale, 2014)

Discoverer: discoverers want to explore new content (Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012), new people and also learn new things. To motivate explorers in the gamified system, the designer should use "access" as a motivator (Dale, 2014).

Survivor: they wish only to demonstrate their superiority over fellow humans (Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012). Survivor's emotions in organizational contexts, such as fear, insecurity encourages people to compete with colleagues and overcome them (Sahdev, 2004).

Figure 1. Customer Gamification Pyramid based on Maslow's Motivation Mechanisms (King, 2013)

The best games and gamified systems should satisfy the needs of all four categories. Even the Survivor may be your friends if they function as elite “power users” or if they galvanize everyone else in a positive way (Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012).

Gamification in knowledge sharing

The study of the related literature shows an abundance of applications of game and game-inspired designs in different contexts like education, health, and training. In other words, managers and the researchers' goals were to improve the human condition to encourage people to engage and participate in works easily (Nacke and Deterding, 2017; Norman, 2004). Foursquare and Stack overflow the contemporary examples of the use of technology and game in another context which is known as “gamification” (Deterding et al., 2011). Deterding et al. (2011) define gamification as “the use of game design elements in non-game contexts.”

By using gamification, companies can capture people's attention, loyalty and innovation ideas, and in return, people receive recognition and reputation (Dale, 2014). Knowledge management has experienced two waves in which most of the projects failed (Lambe, 2008) During the third wave, an organization started to deploy game mechanics (such as rating, receiving a point, and leaderboard based on user activity) in KM programs (such as blogs, wikis, social media, and forums) known as gamification (Shpakova et al., 2016). Siemens as the best example of using game element (such as points) is based on the different culture of countries. Siemens system rewarded participants in KM systems for identifying experts (with more points, you are a knowledgeable person) or in other contexts, where people receive material goods (Shpakova et al., 2016). Stack Overflow portal or Yahoo Answers (Q&A applications) are additional examples of using game elements to motivate people to share their knowledge with others. Despite this successful application, how gamification can motivate people to share their knowledge is opaque. But, by reviewing the knowledge management literature, the main motivator of knowledge sharing, which can be more effective in search, share, and apply the knowledge is recognizable; this motivator includes recognition, reciprocity, and fun or enjoyment which is the key element of the gamified system and flow theory (Dale, 2014; Silic & Back, 2017). Financial rewards are pitted against fun, and in the gamified system, fun is given priority over financial rewards (Dale, 2014); the main problem with many existing KM systems is that they are "not fun" and user's engagement and satisfaction are low (Schacht & Maedche, 2015).

METHODOLOGY

Choosing the appropriate research method is the basis for conducting research and achieving relevant results. The thematic analysis method is used to analyze the semi-structured interview data. The exploratory interview was conducted with 15 TV employees to identify the motivational needs for knowledge sharing.

Sample and data

For conducting research, purposive sampling was used; the diversity of the TV sectors and professions of IRIB was taken into consideration. Due to the qualitative research approach and the need to identify the motivational needs of the staff, authors selected 15 employees from a variety of professions including, TV Channel managers, producers, directors, and writers.

To explore the employee's motivational needs and User-Type in the workplace, semi-structured interview was used as the primary data collection method in this research (Arksey & Knight, 1999; Wilson, 2014). Jennifer Mason argues that semi-structured interviewing is the interactional exchange of dialogue (between two or more participants, in face-to-face or other contexts) (Edwards & Holland, 2013). Regarding the aim of research which is analyzing and solving practical problems in IRIB, the authors used a case study that was suitable for "building and testing business theories" (Dul & Hak, 2007).

Instrument

Data were collected from 15 semi-structured interviews with TV employees of IRIB. The interviews with these employees were conducted face-to-face and took between 30-90 minutes and covered the motivational needs of employees in knowledge sharing. “Do we ask our participants about why they are reluctant to share their knowledge? And what are their motivational needs to share knowledge with colleagues?” These interviews were recorded and then transcribed for analyzing. Interviews were conducted on 29th May – 21st June 2018 with employees of IRIB TV.

Date analysis

The thematic analysis method was used to analyze the collected data in semi-structured interviews with TV employees to identify motivational needs and User-Type. This analysis is done in two-step coding: generating concept and categories. These steps are done in MAXQDA 10.

RESULTS

Motivation

“What are the main motivational needs of TV employees of IRIB to engage in the knowledge sharing process as a collective entrepreneurship?” is our main question from TV employees of IRIB. Based on Table .1 the analysis of interviews in MAXQDA 10 indicates that motivational needs include both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation comprising factors such as status, power, autonomy, security, community, and learning. The most important motivation was identified by the number of sub-categories. The findings reveal that TV employees of IRIB are unwilling to share their knowledge, because they found that the organization does not take any steps to share knowledge amongst employees; due to this negligence, in most cases organization were criticized. Additionally, a dull environment is an impediment to the creativity and self-fulfillment of the employees, hindering them from creating a knowledge-based media product. On the other hand, there are also employees who, regardless of these issues, do not hesitate to transfer experience.

Table 1. Motivational needs of TV employees of IRIB to knowledge sharing (Authors' work)

Number of sub-categories	TV employees of IRIB motivations to knowledge sharing
38	Status
24	Power
15	Autonomy
14	Security
11	Community
8	Learning

Status: Recognition is a primary motive for sharing knowledge based on table 1; in other words, due to their efforts, employees expect to be appreciated by organizations. In knowledge sharing, people desire to acquire status because of their participation in knowledge transfer. Employees expect to be more admired as much as they collaborate and bring achievement to the organization; both inside and outside of the organization and among the audience. The interviewee said:

“The incentive that inspires employees to acquire more knowledge is achieving a desirable job position.”

When employees do not reach their expected positions in the organization, they decide to leave the organization and choose a different environment. This is the fate of the organizations that do not pay enough attention to human resources. The interviewee said:

“We have a problem in an organization that someone gets an experience, fired from or leaves the organization for a professional environment.”

Power: This motive, is one of the most important motivational needs among employees. This motive is more intense among employees. The reason for this lies in the notion that knowledge brings power; employees see their knowledge and skills as a powerful tool to meet their desires; in fact, the knowledge and skills are perceived as an asset, that empowers them.

“If knowledge has the benefit for employees, they will not share it.”

“I have an idea, and if I share this idea with you, you will produce the program, I intended.”

Of course, the motive of power among managers seems to be different; whereas employees are encouraged to share knowledge based on their power and status. In other words, employees who need more power are more stimulated to share knowledge.

“One of the motivating barriers among employees to share their knowledge is power relationships.”

Autonomy: Autonomy in sharing knowledge should take place in the processes. In other words, in line with the main goal, the employees should be given the freedom to share their knowledge in the best way to deal with the issues.

“I would like to say that it was easier for him to act instead of talking. I mean, he was more comfortable in his way and carried out the transfer of knowledge.”

One of the issues that arise in the IRIB's organization, and maybe it can be generalized to all media organizations, is the importance of autonomy in media organizations. It's important to note that the loss of autonomy in the production of media products is an obstacle to the transfer and use of knowledge and additionally reduce liability.

“So how can you transfer the experience of something which your employees are not happy with? They are not even willing to take responsibility. “

Community: based on interviews, the spirit of collaboration to share knowledge among employees, is critical. The motivation to communicate and create a network with employees in the organization encourages people to share knowledge.

“I think one of the main barriers to share knowledge in teamwork is the lack of spirit of cooperation. One who works in the field of teamwork should be involved.“

Learning: Learning and discovering new things is often seen as a powerful incentive for employees, which leads to success in media activity. It can be found from most of the interviews that knowledge is both acquisitive and based on ingenuity and creativity.

“The good aspect of art is that it is endless, which makes people ecstatic. In media, this is reciprocal; sometimes the mentee learns from the mentor, and sometimes I am influenced by the mentee’s work.”

Security: One of the main barriers to knowledge sharing in IRIB is security motive. The dominant attitude among employees is that knowledge as a powerful element that guarantees their job position and even income. The interviewee said:

“ The resource constraints make me avoid sharing knowledge. If someone else gains my knowledge, consequently, I will be deprived of resources.”

“Nobody transfers their knowledge; if knowledge sharing is a threat to him.”

User type

“What are the user-types of TV employees of IRIB in the knowledge sharing process as a collective entrepreneurship?” To answer this question, we refer to the answer of the first question and employee interviews to identify user types. The analysis of the interviews showed that TV employees are categorized into four groups, including achiever, socializer, discoverer, and survivor.

Table 2. User type of TV employees of IRIB to knowledge sharing (Authors’ work)

Number of sub-categories	User type of TV employees of IRIB in knowledge sharing
77	Achiever
14	Survivor
11	Socializer
8	Discoverer

Figure 2. User type of TV employees for knowledge sharing in IRIB (Authors' work)

Achiever: According to Fig. 2, employees have each of four user type, but one of them is strongest, which is an achiever. This type of user prefers to acquire autonomy, power, and status through sharing their own knowledge and experience; therefore, both financial and non-financial incentives are effective to this user type. In other words, the motivation of most employees involves achieving things satisfying their inner needs, such as status, power, and autonomy. These motivations, according to King's hierarchy, lead to spiritual happiness.

Socializer: This type of user (employee), shares knowledge for a sense of collaboration and belonging to IRIB organization. Help to colleagues in problem-solving and sharing knowledge through communication lead the employees to emotional happiness.

Discoverer: A sense of exploration, encourages employees to learn and gain knowledge. Based on Fig. 2, in the discoverer type, employees learn to be motivated to share their knowledge. How can they be successful in their professions? As mentioned above, media and art are endless, and this feature encourages employees to learn more.

Survivor: At the bottom of the hierarchy, survivors are seen. They want security. Otherwise, they do not accept to transfer knowledge with colleagues. From the perspective of survivors, knowledge brings security.

DISCUSSION

This paper aims to answer the question of what the motivating factors and user-type of TV employees of IRIB are in the knowledge sharing process. The intent was to broaden our understanding of media employees and design the gamified knowledge sharing system properly. We identified six main motivators in the knowledge sharing context in the TV of Iran Broadcasting, including power, status, autonomy, community, learning, and security. Additionally, achieving these needs help us to identify the personality and user type. According to the theoretical literature, users are divided into four categories in the face of a game system: achiever, socializer, discoverer, and survivor.

Status: Media production is based on the participation and collaboration of media employees. The desire to join a community is a feature of the media business, which is more visible in activities such as filmmaking and television program production. The relevance of this subject to the status is that employees who have the knowledge about the field of media production, psychologically, are less commonly accepted as part of an organization, and this issue affects their social status in the organization. Because the status is associated with the recognition in the knowledge sharing process, this motive needs more investigation by the media management researchers (Wang et al., 2014). An employee earns status and recognition by sharing their knowledge and showing their expertise to others (Andriessen, 2006; Rahab & Wahyuni, 2013). An employee who has been motivated to share knowledge by status, considered as an achiever; based on the Four-Drives theory of motivation, these types of users want to forge a relationship with a co-worker and receive recognition and status (Perryer et al., 2016).

Power: In fact, the motive of power stems from the nature of media organizations; because media organization, in particular, public broadcasting organizations have a wide range of audience. Employees of these organizations are motivated to produce creative media products and attract the attention of the audience. Even content providers are sometimes more powerful than the head of the organization; the knowledge and skills of these people are considered as a powerful tool and an asset, which can turn into power, a power gained from the audience. So an employee showing their expertise to gain power (Andriessen, 2006) is considered as an example of the intrinsic reward in some research studies (Dale, 2014); According to the theory of Maslow, individuals need power (Andriessen, 2006); power in King's customer gamification pyramid is incorporated in achiever type. So, an employee who has the power motivation to share knowledge is considered as an achiever.

Autonomy: autonomy in IRIB reflects self-actualization in hierarchy needs of Maslow; As a consequence, autonomy is considered as an achiever. Hendriks (1999) introduces autonomy as the main motivational need for knowledge sharing. By enhancing autonomy, the employees will share their knowledge. Küng (2008) mentioned that autonomy-based processes develop creativity because the sense of ownership and, therefore, the internal motivation intensify and allow employees to deal with issues in a way that they can use most of their skills. The lack of autonomy in sharing knowledge prevents the flow of human resource knowledge into the system, thus affecting organizational efficiency and effectiveness and productivity of work.

Community: Relatedness to others may reflect belongingness in the hierarchy needs of Maslow. Achieving a creative and knowledge-based media product is not possible without collaboration. Media organizations need employees who are motivated to communicate and collaborate. Küng (2008) says attention needs to be given to the team's communication skills, otherwise, required expertise and insights will not be shared, particularly the tacit knowledge that emerges during the project. The sense of belonging and being a member of the family or community among TV employees points to bond drive (Perryer et al., 2016); Based on this drive, the employee is considered as a socializer. Socializers want to engage with friends and co-workers (Werbach Kevin & Hunter Dan, 2012) and "win together".

Learning: Modern media organizations and media professionals need to continuously learn because these organizations are constantly changing. Based on the four-drive theory, the opportunity to be challenged to learn new things and update their knowledge about new techniques are seen as strong incentives for employees. This leads to success in media work (Perryer et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2014) (Andriessen, 2006). Learning as an incentive satisfies the self-actualization need. But, in King's customer gamification pyramid, it is assumed as the motivations of discoverers.

Security: When the organizational psychological atmosphere transmits the feel of insecurity to the employees, they become conservative and focus solely on their own success and individual work. Andriessen (2006) points to security as a motivational need for knowledge sharing; Therefore, incentives such as job security, progress opportunity, high salary, receiving services and rewards have a positive impact. An employee who has been motivated by security is a survivor. In the organizational context, employee reaction includes emotions like fear, insecurity, and anger.

CONCLUSION

"What are the main motivational needs of TV employees of IRIB to engage in knowledge sharing process as a collective entrepreneurship?" Lack of motivation is the main barrier to share the knowledge among staff and foster entrepreneurship team. Considering this problem and according to the new motivational techniques, it

is important to improve collective entrepreneurship. In this research, we focused on the motivation of media staff that was disregarded by most media management and entrepreneurship scholars. Our findings suggest that organizational entrepreneurship strategies should be designed based on identified different motivational triggers and user types that support creative and innovative behaviors. In IRIB, employees have different attitudes toward knowledge sharing and, not everyone shares their knowledge for their own reasons. Their motivational needs for knowledge sharing indicate that TV employees, mostly motivated by intrinsic motivations, including status, power, autonomy, community, learning. Status and power are the strongest motives that are largely ignored by the managers; and employees who fail to achieve these motives, leave the organization. Learning in the entrepreneurial environment is critical, but among TV employees it is not viewed as important, and IRIB managers should reinforce this type of motivation, on the other hand, security is the most basic and common motivation among employees. User type of employees includes achiever, socializer, discoverer, and survivor. Because of the dominance of achiever user type in IRIB, they should be awarded intrinsic motives in a gamified system.

In this paper, the authors focused on the areas that have been ignored by most of the media management scholars and also regarded gamification as a new trend for promoting entrepreneurship in media firms. In other words, this study focused on the fun layer, which is the main issue of existing knowledge sharing systems and identified the main motivational needs of media staff that create a sense of happiness and motivation to participate in organizational entrepreneurship.

Our study is limited to the Iranian context and public service media organization. The second limitation of our research is the scarcity of literature, studies and theoretical knowledge about media entrepreneurship and also knowledge sharing in media businesses. As suggested research for the future, the researchers can focus on the examination of motivational needs and user-types of employees engaged in knowledge sharing in non-public media firms. Also, gamification can be considered in future research as a solution (like using game mechanics, dynamics and aesthetics) to stimulate employees.

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